

TECHNOLOGY OF IMPROVING PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF STUDENTS OF PEDAGOGY AND PSYCHOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF CONTINUOUS PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE

Botirova Yorqinoy Dilshod qizi

Gulistan State University, Pedagogy and psychology, 2-course master's degree

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5608355>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15th October 2021
Accepted: 20th October 2021
Online: 25th October 2021

KEY WORDS

People's Teacher, Shuhrat Medal, On Education

ABSTRACT

Currently, the Republic of Uzbekistan is actively working to constantly improve the professional skills, knowledge and abilities of young teachers and psychologists.

Also, during the years of independence, 3425 teachers and psychologists in the public education system of the republic have been awarded various state awards and titles for outstanding achievements in pedagogical activities and selfless work. Six of them were awarded the title of "Hero of Uzbekistan", 302 - "People's Teacher of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and 319 - "Honored Worker of Public Education of Uzbekistan", 101 21 were awarded the Order of El-Yurt Hurmati, 21 were awarded the Order of Fidokorona Hizmatlari Uchun, and 1229 were awarded the Shuhrat Medal. The national model, highlighted in the "National Program of Personnel Training", takes into account the national and territorial features of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the image of a cadre (specialist) - a well-rounded person and a mature specialist, trained on the basis of advanced science, engineering

and technology. The role of teachers in the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the "National Training Program" is extremely unique. Only a highly experienced teacher of the XXI century can fulfill the task of teaching and educating children of the XXI century, bringing them to the level of harmoniously developed people and highly qualified specialists. educating young people teaches them to live with pain and to see the future clearly. Each teacher teaches to use their abilities, knowledge and experience to conscientiously imagine and accurately implement the current problems, goals and objectives of our country, as well as to develop the skills of a creative approach to pedagogical activity. In the science of pedagogy, there are different definitions of the concept of "pedagogical skill": pedagogical skill is a high level of

pedagogical activity, which is reflected in the ability of the teacher to achieve optimal results in a given time. (N.V.Kuzmina, N.V.Kuxarev); "Synthesis of scientific knowledge, skills, methodical art and personal qualities of the teacher" (AlSherbakov);

"High level of pedagogical activity, knowledge, skills and competencies in the specialty and a set of professionally important qualities" (Pedagogical Dictionary);

"The complex of personality traits that ensure a high level of organization of professional activity (humanistic orientation of teachers, professional knowledge, professional skills and pedagogical techniques" (IA Zyazyun); In order to restore and further enhance our national identity, improve the national education system, strengthen its national base, bring it up to world standards and skills in line with modern requirements, great creative work is being done in the education system. The Law of the Republic

of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the Law "On the National Training Program" adopted at the IX session of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan It is noted that there is an honorable and responsible task, such as educating a harmoniously developed generation. Article 3 of the law declares education as a priority area in the social development of the Republic of Uzbekistan and sets out the following basic principles of state policy in the field of education. "A teacher should be involved in science on a regular basis. Otherwise, it will look like a dead tree or a rock. Just as a dried tree and a stone cannot bear fruit, no such result can be expected from a teacher in the future. " is important. If in the past a major discovery in a field of science was an effective and hard-to-believe event for almost fifteen years, now every year, even every month, new discoveries are made in the field of science and technology. new trends that are unknown are emerging.

References:

1. Pedagogy and psychology. Sh. Aliboyeva, T. Yorqulov. Tashkent: 2010. Textbook. 230 b.
2. www.Ziyonet.uz
3. www.Now.org